

Practice Abstracts – batch 1

D7.7

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	28.01.2026	Nora Brüggemann (CSCP)	Review of the full text, corrections related to phrasing and edits in the text. Suggestions related to the structure and layout of the practice abstracts and the deliverable.
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1.0	09.02.2026	Deitze Otaduy (UDEUSTO)	Submission, final version.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Meaning
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization (United Nations)
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
FLWPR	Food Loss and Waste Prevention and Reduction
PA	Practice Abstract

1. Executive Summary

1.1. Project Overview

If food loss and waste (FLW) were a country, it would be the third leading cause of greenhouse gas emissions. FLW also burdens waste management systems and exacerbates food insecurity, contributing significantly to the three global crises of climate change, nature and biodiversity loss, and pollution and waste.

PRECIOUS, a transdisciplinary alliance of 18 entities from 11 EU countries, believes that reliable data on the environmental impacts of FLW is crucial for accelerating EU progress towards climate targets and reducing environmental impacts (including biodiversity) across the food supply chain. The project's collective understanding is that the challenge goes beyond measuring the amount of food saved or CO2 emissions. When food is wasted, valuable and limited resources such as water, land use, and energy are lost, while 8.9% of the worldwide population is suffering from hunger according to FAO, therefore, depleting the planet's natural resources. It is critical to broaden our understanding of the issue to transform the food system and raise public awareness that motivates change.

PRECIOUS aims to contribute to the transformation of food systems by addressing existing data gaps and developing a unified and openly accessible evaluation framework to quantify the economic, environmental, and social impacts of strategies to reduce FLW, considering potential rebound effects.

The project will engage stakeholders from 2 Use Cases (Spain and Greece) and 3 Co-creation and Replication Nodes (Poland, Lithuania, Hungary) to address systemic causes across geographical boundaries. The project aims to induce a fundamental change in attitudes and behaviors towards food consumption and disposal through collaborative efforts and innovative methods, fostering a more just and sustainable EU food system.

1.2. Deliverable Summary

The project aims to generate credible and sustainable scientific, societal and economic/technological impacts. The development of a topic-specific guidance on actions that address FLW is one of the main activities being developed during the project. It is focused on the lessons learnt from past and current FLW prevention actions and will serve as a main guidance to support different types of actors from the food system to design and decide on their efforts towards zero FLW. The “practice abstracts” (PAs) are short summaries that describe a main information/recommendation/practice that can be used by end-users in their daily practice. This deliverable contains the first three practice abstracts out of 10 that G!E is going to deliver by the end of the PRECIOUS project. The practice abstracts are going to be uploaded to the project's website and disseminated in the EIP-AGRI common format (attached in the Annex) on the [EU CAP Network website](#) with open access for practitioners and the public.

2. Introduction

Practice Abstracts:

Under the EIP-AGRI, [Operational Groups](#) and [Horizon projects](#) work in close synergy to stimulate knowledge exchange and spread innovative solutions across the EU. Operational Groups and Horizon projects are expected to share their results and practice-oriented solutions in concise summaries, known as ‘**practice abstracts**’. Practice abstracts follow the ‘EIP-AGRI common format to promote a more harmonised and practice-oriented way of sharing results.

Practice abstracts in the EIP-AGRI common format:

- help projects share their results in an easily understandable way for farmers, foresters, rural communities and others from practice
- foster knowledge flows, and shares project results more widely and at a faster pace
- support the development of project proposals with added value, avoiding duplication of ongoing or completed projects
- facilitate networking by connecting project partners with farmers, foresters and others from practice
- answer to real needs from the field

The practice abstracts (PA) are among the most efficient instruments for communication and dissemination, offering practical knowledge for food value chain actors to better understand how they can adopt small-scale solutions. By summarising and showcasing good examples, the PRECIOUS PAs will inspire and support a wider group of food value chain actors across Europe to cooperate and bring FLWRP actions based innovation to market.

The European Innovation Partnership AGRI (EIP-AGRI) common format is a thematic network that helps projects to work in synergy with other interactive innovation projects under the Framework Programme “Horizon”. These Horizon "multi-actor projects" and "thematic networks" act at EU level and bring together partners from at least three countries. All Horizon multi-actor projects and thematic networks, as well as all EIP-AGRI Operational Groups, use the common format to target groups, end users or whoever is interested with short and concise practical information (so called 'practice abstracts'). Links to audio-visual material (photos, films, etc.) are included as much as possible. The use of the EIP-AGRI common format facilitates not only the exchange of knowledge, but also the contact between potential partners in innovation projects. It contributes to building up a unique repository of practical knowledge across the EU via the EIP-AGRI [project database](#), which supports the dissemination of results of all interactive innovation projects.

3. Methodology

The development of the practice abstracts was discussed during Project Technical Committee meetings and possible topics were suggested by partners. After a few meetings, the Technical Committee determined the final structure and topics of the first batch (3) of the practice abstracts. Three partners (EIT, CSCP, TUB) were chosen to author the PAs and G!E provided guidance for partners on how to prepare these summaries:

- The practice abstract shall provide concise information (maximum two pages) on the main features of the project.
- It should include the objective of the project describing the problems and/or opportunities the project addresses
- The practice abstracts should provide exact recommendations for practitioners, target groups and end users in a concise, easily understandable format. What would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results? Any important practical details?
- It should include a short summary of the findings (expected or final). This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements, which are particularly relevant for practitioners
- Research-oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

Topics were chosen in accordance with the state of the project and relevance for target audiences and practitioners. As the project is still in its early stages, the current batch builds on the literature review and expertise of the selected partners; and focuses on methodological approaches and future outcomes, rather than exact project results. The first three topics to be included at this stage of the project were:

- Educational campaigns and workshops, raising awareness for young people.
- Consumer acceptance of upcycled foods.
- Stakeholder participation in Food Loss and Waste Prevention actions.

G!E coordinated the production of the PAs in accordance with the previously agreed format. Upon receipt of the initial versions from the authors, G!E made sure they complied with the said format and created a design template that can be used for the publication of the full PAs on the project website. As the original (full text) PAs were not completely adapted to the EIP-AGRI common format, G!E edited and formatted the text and created an EIP-AGRI format compliant versions without compromising the original PAs main points.

The following section (4) showcases the original (full text) PAs, while the final files to be uploaded on the website are presented in Annex 2. The edited EIP-AGRI common format versions are presented in Annex 3.

4. Full practice abstracts

4.1. Raising Awareness and Reducing Food Loss and Waste Among Young generations

Author: Leticia Lopez, EIT Food, leticia.lopez@eitfood.eu

Food loss and waste (FLW) remain a significant global challenge, with profound environmental, economic, and social implications. Despite increasing awareness of its impact, younger generations often lack access to engaging, age-appropriate educational resources that help them understand FLW and adopt preventive behaviours. Current educational activities are often fragmented, poorly integrated into everyday life, and not tailored to the learning needs of children, adolescents, or young adults. These gaps limit the development of sustainable habits at home, at school, and in wider communities, making it difficult to achieve meaningful behavioural change in the long term.

To address these challenges, EIT Food is developing a comprehensive educational campaign targeting young generations. This campaign combines digital and physical resources, including videos, infographics, and interactive tools, designed to enhance knowledge, foster critical thinking, and promote practical actions to prevent FLW. Materials are incorporated into existing platforms such as [Los Salvacomidas](#) and the [EIT Food Educators Programme](#), ensuring scalability and adaptability across educational contexts.

As part of PRECIOUS, two pilot workshops will be conducted in Spain and Greece for school communities. These workshops will provide hands-on experiences, demonstrating creative ways to repurpose food, plan meals efficiently, and will make informed shopping choices. They will also encourage cross-cultural learning by exploring traditional Spanish and Greek practices related to food sustainability. Complementary university-level activities, led by the University of Jaume I, integrate FLW prevention insights into sustainability and business curricula, fostering systemic understanding among future professionals.

This integrated approach ensures that educational resources and workshops are evidence-based, interactive, and culturally sensitive. By combining digital tools, participatory exercises, and cross-institutional collaboration, the campaign aims to increase awareness, encourage behavioural change, and create a sustainable network of engaged young citizens capable of influencing broader food systems.

Recommendations

- Ensure age-specific design of materials to balance scientific rigour with accessibility, particularly for primary and secondary school audiences.
- Prioritize experiential learning, integrating practical exercises, such as meal planning challenges or food-repurposing tasks, to strengthen real-life application of concepts.
- Strengthen continuity across education levels, ensuring alignment between school-focused materials, university curricula, and community activities to maximize long-term impact.
- Facilitate collaboration among schools, universities, and local organisations, creating multi-actor networks that reinforce behavioural change and extend the reach of FLW-prevention initiatives.
- Engage proactively with educational centres, prioritizing schools already connected to our ecosystem to ensure smooth implementation and maximized impact.
- Equip teaching staff with high-quality, ready-to-use educational resources, providing clear value and tangible benefits for schools participating in the programme.

Keywords

Food Loss and Waste, education, youth engagement, sustainability, behavioural change, workshops, circular food systems, PRECIOUS, Los Salvacomidas

4.2. Consumer Acceptance of Upcycled Foods – Recommendations for Practitioners

Author: Dr. Sebastian Isbanner, TU Berlin, sebastian.isbanner@tu-berlin.de

Upcycled foods are products made from safe, edible ingredients that would otherwise not go to human consumption, such as by-products, surplus or “ugly” produce. They are increasingly discussed as a way to reduce food loss and waste while creating extra value in the food system (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2023; Moshtaghian et al., 2021). Upcycled ingredients can also replace some artificial additives with natural components recovered from side streams (Pinela et al., 2024).

However, upcycled foods are still unfamiliar to most consumers. A recent scoping review of 37 studies shows that awareness and understanding of upcycled foods are generally low, even among people who care about food waste and sustainability (Lu et al., 2024). As with other novel foods, many consumers are cautious about safety, processing and “unnaturalness”, and the word “waste” can trigger negative associations (Günden et al., 2024; Laureati et al., 2024). At the same time, food businesses are under pressure to act on food waste and sustainability targets and therefore need practical guidance on how to design, position and communicate upcycled products that people will actually buy and trust (Moshtaghian et al., 2021).

Who is most open to upcycled foods?

The scoping review by Lu et al. (2024) finds that acceptance tends to be higher among consumers who are more educated, environmentally concerned, aware of food waste, and less neophobic towards new foods and technologies. Similar patterns appear in work on upcycled biscuits and olive leaf products: interest is higher among consumers already engaged with local, organic or sustainable foods (Grasso & Asioli, 2020; Perito et al., 2020).

Generational differences also matter. Zhang et al. (2020) show that Gen Z, Gen Y and Baby Boomers express higher purchase intentions than Gen X, who are more sceptical about quality. Segment studies in Sweden identify “inclined” and “hesitant” consumers with distinct motives: ethical concerns and environmental impact are particularly important for the more accepting group (Moshtaghian et al., 2024a, 2024b).

Which product types and ingredients work best?

Across countries, consumers clearly prefer plant-based upcycled ingredients (fruit, vegetables, grains, seeds) over animal-based ones (Grasso et al., 2023; Lu et al., 2024). Familiar “carrier” products such as bread, biscuits, snack bars and beverages work particularly well, because adding fibre, antioxidants or protein feels natural in these categories (Grasso & Asioli, 2020; Perito et al., 2020).

Case studies illustrate this: Italian consumers show good acceptance of “local and organic” foods with upcycled olive leaves (Perito et al., 2020), and New Zealand consumers are open to upcycled craft beer when taste and quality cues are strong (Goodman-Smith et al., 2023). In Sweden, public preferences emphasize food safety, nutrition and environmental impact when judging upcycled foods (Moshtaghian et al., 2023).

Overall, sensory quality, safety and “normal” appearance remain non-negotiable. People may like the idea of reducing waste, but they still decide mainly on taste, quality and convenience (Günden et al., 2024; Laureati et al., 2024).

How should we define and communicate “upcycled”?

Scholars and industry now converge on definitions that stress three elements: (1) using ingredients that would otherwise be wasted or lost, (2) turning them into foods for human consumption, and (3) doing so in a way that adds value and reduces environmental impact (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2023; Moshtaghian et al., 2021).

For consumers, the language needs to be simple and concrete. Upcycled foods are more easily accepted when described as “using safe surplus ingredients to avoid waste and protect the environment”, rather than focusing on “waste” or complex technology (Lu et al., 2024). Communication experiments show that:

- Frugality framing – emphasizing “not wasting good food” and traditional thrift – increases acceptance of upcycled foods across several European countries (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2022).
- Sustainability claims can increase willingness to pay, especially for indulgent “vice” products, when the environmental benefit is clear (Ghazanfar et al., 2023).
- Mental simulation prompts – asking consumers to imagine trying and enjoying an upcycled product – can raise purchase intentions, particularly when people care about their future self (Yang et al., 2021).
- Clear logos, labels and third-party certifications help signal trust and sustainability, provided they are not overly complex (Lu et al., 2024; Moshtaghan et al., 2021).

Pricing and perceived value

Choice experiments suggest that many consumers expect upcycled products to be similarly priced to, or cheaper than, conventional options, especially when they associate them with by-products or “waste” (Grasso & Asioli, 2020; Zhang et al., 2020). At the same time, a smaller segment is willing to pay a premium if multiple benefits (health, sustainability, quality) are clearly communicated and backed by credible labels (Ghazanfar et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2021).

Practical recommendations for practitioners and businesses

Based on this literature, some concrete suggestions for producers, retailers and communicators are:

- Choose the right product and ingredient!
Focus on plant-based, upcycled ingredients in familiar formats, such as bread, biscuits, snack bars, and drinks. Where possible, link upcycled ingredients to existing quality cues (e.g. local, organic, traditional recipes).
- Make safety, quality and taste highly visible.
Ensure upcycled products look, taste and feel like “normal” food (or better). Clearly state that ingredients are safe and hygienically processed; avoid the word “waste” altogether.
- Use simple, positive framing.
Explain upcycling briefly in consumer-friendly terms: avoiding waste and protecting the environment. Emphasize frugality and resourcefulness alongside sustainability.
- Support decisions with labels and stories.
Use recognizable logos and certifications to signal upcycled content and environmental benefits. Tell short, concrete origin stories and, invite consumers to imagine themselves enjoying the product.
- Position on value, not just virtue.
Avoid large price premiums unless health and sustainability benefits are very clear. For mainstream segments, frame upcycled products as “smart, good-value choices” that are both tasty and responsible.

Taken together, the evidence suggests that upcycled foods can become an accepted part of more circular, resilient food systems – if they are designed and communicated in a way that fits everyday consumer preferences, concerns and habits rather than asking people to compromise on taste, safety or value. At the same time, research on consumer acceptance of upcycled foods is still emerging, and different product types and contexts can evoke different levels of acceptance, so these patterns should be seen as guidance rather than fixed rules.

Keywords

Upcycled foods, Food waste reduction, Consumer acceptance, Sustainable food systems, Circular economy in food, Food loss and waste prevention, Sustainability communication, Consumer behaviour in food choices.

Please consult the list of references in the Annex.

4.3. Using Process Flows to Increase Value for Stakeholder Participation in Food Loss and Waste Prevention

Author: Luca E. Sander, CSCP, luca.emanuel-sander@cscp.org

Food Loss and Waste Prevention and Reduction (FLWPR) can be a complex undertaking, especially when considering dynamics across supply chain stages. Accordingly, FLWPR projects often produce multiple tools and outputs across parallel timelines. At the same time, apart from in-depth case studies, stakeholders of the various food supply chain stages, as well as policy makers, and civil society have a limited availability to test and integrate these outputs, since they often participate on a voluntary basis. This creates a challenge for both, the project partners and the participating stakeholders, as the project partners will have less feedback on their developed outputs, while stakeholders may have difficulties to perceive the added value for their operations.

Thus, it is important to create an overview of how the various project outputs serve the interests of the stakeholders. This can be partly done by co-creating a clear vision and mission for stakeholder engagement formats, such as the Communities of Practice (CoPs) within PRECIOUS. We suggest going further by thinking about how each tool, developed under a project, can be integrated into the stakeholders' activities to reduce FLW. To this end, a user-centric process flow approach can help, following a similar logic as in other projects, which have used flow diagrams as boundary objects communicating between researchers and stakeholders (i.e. Merck et al., 2023).

A process-based perspective may begin by asking: What process would a stakeholder follow to achieve effective FLW prevention and reduction in their context? Mapping this journey into a clear process flow helps project partners align tools with stakeholder needs and guides both parties toward practical, action-oriented discussions. It also turns diverse project outputs into an integrated support pathway, showing stakeholders where they are in the process and what support is available at each step. In PRECIOUS, this approach is operationalized through a six-step process, which is grounded in the experiences of running behaviour change interventions and FLWPR-specific interventions under the Academy of Change and Chorizo projects, respectively (Strube & Nicolau, 2019; ICLEI European Secretariat, 2025).

Six Steps Used in PRECIOUS

The PRECIOUS project aims to reduce food loss and waste across all stages of the food supply chain. As a result, the process flow diagram was kept simple, focusing on the essential steps of designing and implementing FLWPR interventions. The attached diagram illustrates how various tools and outputs developed under PRECIOUS will provide value for stakeholders along each step. In addition to providing clear guidance on the type of support, which stakeholders can expect across supply chains, it also helps to integrate the various project activities in a practice-oriented manner.

Key Takeaways for Practitioners

- Map project outputs onto a user-centric process flow, providing a clear overview of tools and insights that a project can deliver towards the overarching objective.
- Process flows highlight how a complex project provides added value to (often voluntarily) participating stakeholders.
- The process flow can help to better integrate the various project activities.

- The mapping of the process provides an entry point to integrate the project’s need for stakeholder feedback with stakeholders’ interest in FLWPR.

Using a process-based approach allows research and innovation projects to frame project outputs in a way that is practical, intuitive, and aligned with stakeholder needs. It not only supports more meaningful engagement but also fosters stronger integration across diverse project activities—ultimately increasing the impact of food loss and waste prevention efforts.

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Keywords

Food loss and waste prevention, Stakeholder engagement, Process flow, Communities of Practice, Co-creation, Food supply chain sustainability, User-centric tools, Research-to-practice integration

Annex 1

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Annex 2 – Full practice abstracts, designed version

Please see the following pages.

Raising Awareness and Reducing Food Loss and Waste Among Young Generations

Practice Abstract #1

Author: Leticia Lopez, EIT Food

leticia.lopez@eitfood.eu

Food loss and waste (FLW) remains a significant global challenge, with profound environmental, economic, and social implications. Despite increasing awareness of its impact, younger generations often lack access to engaging, age-appropriate educational resources that help them understand FLW and adopt preventive behaviours. Current educational activities are often fragmented, poorly integrated into everyday life, and not tailored to the learning needs of children, adolescents, or young adults. These gaps limit the development of sustainable habits at home, at school, and in wider communities, making it difficult to achieve meaningful behavioural change in the long term.

To address these challenges, EIT Food is developing a comprehensive educational campaign targeting young generations. This campaign combines digital and physical resources, including videos, infographics, and interactive tools, designed to enhance knowledge, foster critical thinking, and promote practical actions to prevent FLW. Materials are incorporated into existing platforms such as [Los Salvacomidas](#) and the [EIT Food Educators Programme](#), ensuring scalability and adaptability across educational contexts.

As part of PRECIOUS, two pilot workshops will be conducted in Spain and Greece for school communities. These workshops provide hands-on experiences, demonstrating creative ways to repurpose food, plan meals efficiently, and make informed shopping choices. They also encourage cross-cultural learning by exploring traditional Spanish and Greek practices related to food sustainability. Complementary university-level activities, led by the University of Jaume I, integrate FLW prevention insights into sustainability and business curricula, fostering systemic understanding among future professionals.

This integrated approach ensures that educational resources and workshops are evidence-based, interactive, and culturally sensitive. By combining digital tools, participatory exercises, and cross-institutional collaboration, the campaign aims to increase awareness, encourage behavioural change, and create a sustainable network of engaged young citizens capable of influencing broader food systems.

Recommendations

- Ensure age-specific design of materials to balance scientific rigour with accessibility, particularly for primary and secondary school audiences.
- Prioritise experiential learning, integrating practical exercises, such as meal planning challenges or food-repurposing tasks, to strengthen real-life application of concepts.
- Strengthen continuity across education levels, ensuring alignment between school-focused materials, university curricula, and community activities to maximise long-term impact.
- Facilitate collaboration among schools, universities, and local organisations, creating multi-actor networks that reinforce behavioural change and extend the reach of FLW-prevention initiatives.
- Engage proactively with educational centres, prioritising schools already connected to our ecosystem to ensure smooth implementation and maximised impact.
- Equip teaching staff with high-quality, ready-to-use educational resources, providing clear value and tangible benefits for schools participating in the programme.

Keywords

Food Loss and Waste, education, youth engagement, sustainability, behavioural change, workshops, circular food systems, PRECIOUS, Los Salvacomidas

About

Coordinated by the University of Deusto and comprising of 18 partners from 11 different European countries, the EU-funded PRECIOUS project seeks to build a systemic, multi-actor approach to Food Loss and Waste (FLW) prevention. The project will develop and share a standardised database of effective FLW prevention and reduction actions, addressing both their benefits and potential rebound effects. It also aims to create holistic methodologies that engage diverse food system stakeholders, incorporating sustainability science, climate change considerations, biodiversity preservation, and policy priorities into an integrated framework.

www.precious-horizon.eu

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Consumer Acceptance of Upcycled Foods – Recommendations for Practitioners

Practice Abstract #2

Author: Dr. Sebastian Isbanner, TU Berlin

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Upcycled foods are products made from safe, edible ingredients that would otherwise not go to human consumption, such as by-products, surplus or “ugly” produce. They are increasingly discussed as a way to reduce food loss and waste while creating extra value in the food system (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2023; Moshtaghian et al., 2021). Upcycled ingredients can also replace some artificial additives with natural components recovered from side streams (Pinela et al., 2024).

However, upcycled foods are still unfamiliar to most consumers. A recent scoping review of 37 studies shows that awareness and understanding of upcycled foods are generally low, even among people who care about food waste and sustainability (Lu et al., 2024). As with other novel foods, many consumers are cautious about safety, processing and “unnaturalness”, and the word “waste” can trigger negative associations (Günden et al., 2024; Laureati et al., 2024). At the same time, food businesses are under pressure to act on food waste and sustainability targets and therefore need practical guidance on how to design, position and communicate upcycled products that people will actually buy and trust (Moshtaghian et al., 2021).

Who is most open to upcycled foods?

The scoping review by Lu et al. (2024) finds that acceptance tends to be higher among consumers who are more educated, environmentally concerned, aware of food waste, and less neophobic towards new foods and technologies. Similar patterns appear in work on upcycled biscuits and olive leaf products: interest is higher among consumers already engaged with local, organic or sustainable foods (Grasso & Asioli, 2020; Perito et al., 2020).

Generational differences also matter. Zhang et al. (2020) show that Gen Z, Gen Y and Baby Boomers express higher purchase intentions than Gen X, who are more sceptical about quality. Segment studies in Sweden identify “inclined” and “hesitant” consumers with distinct motives: ethical concerns and environmental impact are particularly important for the more accepting group (Moshtaghian et al., 2024a, 2024b).

Which product types and ingredients work best?

Across countries, consumers clearly prefer plant-based upcycled ingredients (fruit, vegetables, grains, seeds) over animal-based ones (Grasso et al., 2023; Lu et al., 2024). Familiar “carrier” products such as bread, biscuits,

snack bars and beverages work particularly well, because adding fibre, antioxidants or protein feels natural in these categories (Grasso & Asioli, 2020; Perito et al., 2020).

Case studies illustrate this: Italian consumers show good acceptance of “local and organic” foods with upcycled olive leaves (Perito et al., 2020), and New Zealand consumers are open to upcycled craft beer when taste and quality cues are strong (Goodman-Smith et al., 2023). In Sweden, public preferences emphasise food safety, nutrition and environmental impact when judging upcycled foods (Moshtaghian et al., 2023).

Overall, sensory quality, safety and “normal” appearance remain non-negotiable. People may like the idea of reducing waste, but they still decide mainly on taste, quality and convenience (Günden et al., 2024; Laureati et al., 2024).

How should we define and communicate “upcycled”?

Scholars and industry now converge on definitions that stress three elements: (1) using ingredients that would otherwise be wasted or lost, (2) turning them into foods for human consumption, and (3) doing so in a way that adds value and reduces environmental impact (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2023; Moshtaghian et al., 2021).

For consumers, the language needs to be simple and concrete. Upcycled foods are more easily accepted when described as “using safe surplus ingredients to avoid waste and protect the environment”, rather than focusing on “waste” or complex technology (Lu et al., 2024). Communication experiments show that:

- Frugality framing – emphasising “not wasting good food” and traditional thrift – increases acceptance of upcycled foods across several European countries (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2022).
- Sustainability claims can increase willingness to pay, especially for indulgent “vice” products, when the environmental benefit is clear (Ghazanfar et al., 2023).
- Mental simulation prompts – asking consumers to imagine trying and enjoying an upcycled product – can raise purchase intentions, particularly when people care about their future self (Yang et al., 2021).
- Clear logos, labels and third-party certifications help signal trust and sustainability, provided they are not overly complex (Lu et al., 2024; Moshtaghian et al., 2021).

Pricing and perceived value

Choice experiments suggest that many consumers expect upcycled products to be similarly priced to, or cheaper than, conventional options, especially when they associate them with by-products or “waste” (Grasso & Asioli, 2020; Zhang et al., 2020). At the same time, a smaller segment is willing to pay a premium if multiple benefits (health, sustainability, quality) are clearly communicated and backed by credible labels (Ghazanfar et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2021).

Practical recommendations for practitioners and businesses

Based on this literature, some concrete suggestions for producers, retailers and communicators are:

- Choose the right product and ingredient!

Focus on plant-based, upcycled ingredients in familiar formats, such as bread, biscuits, snack bars, and drinks. Where possible, link upcycled ingredients to existing quality cues (e.g. local, organic, traditional recipes).

- Make safety, quality and taste highly visible

Ensure upcycled products look, taste and feel like “normal” food (or better). Clearly state that ingredients are safe and hygienically processed; avoid language that foregrounds “waste” (or the word “waste” altogether).

- Use simple, positive framing.

Explain upcycling briefly in consumer-friendly terms: avoiding waste and protecting the environment. Emphasise frugality and resourcefulness (“not wasting good food”) alongside sustainability.

- Support decisions with labels and stories.

Use recognisable logos and certifications to signal upcycled content and environmental benefits. Tell short, concrete origin stories and, where appropriate, invite consumers to imagine themselves enjoying the product.

- Position on value, not just virtue.

Avoid large price premiums unless health and sustainability benefits are very clear. For mainstream segments, frame upcycled products as “smart, good-value choices” that are both tasty and responsible.

Taken together, the evidence suggests that upcycled foods can become an accepted part of more circular, resilient food systems – if they are designed and communicated in a way that fits everyday consumer preferences, concerns and habits rather than asking people to compromise on taste, safety or value. At the same time, research on consumer acceptance of upcycled foods is still emerging, and different product types and contexts can evoke different levels of acceptance, so these patterns should be seen as guidance rather than fixed rules.

Please consult the list of references in the Annexe on the next page.

Keywords

Upcycled foods, Food waste reduction, Consumer acceptance, Sustainable food systems, Circular economy in food, Food loss and waste prevention, Sustainability communication, Consumer behaviour in food choices

About

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Using Process Flows to Increase Value for Stakeholder Participation in Food Loss and Waste Prevention

Practice Abstract #3

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Food Loss and Waste Prevention and Reduction (FLWPR) can be a complex undertaking, especially when considering dynamics across supply chain stages. Accordingly, FLWPR projects often produce multiple tools and outputs across parallel timelines. At the same time, apart from in-depth case studies, stakeholders of the various food supply chain stages, as well as policy makers, and civil society have a limited availability to test and integrate these outputs, since they often participate on a voluntary basis. This creates a challenge for both, the project partners and the participating stakeholders, as the project partners will have less feedback on their developed outputs, while stakeholders may have difficulties to perceive the added value for their operations.

Thus, it is important to create an overview of how the various project outputs serve the interests of the stakeholders. This can be partly done by co-creating a clear vision and mission for stakeholder engagement formats, such as the Communities of Practice within PRECIOUS. We suggest going further by thinking about how each tool, developed under a project, can be integrated into the stakeholders' activities to reduce FLW. To this end, a user-centric process flow approach can help, following a similar logic as in other projects, which have used flow diagrams as boundary objects communicating between researchers and stakeholders (i.e. Merck et al., 2023).

A process-based perspective may begin by asking: What process would a stakeholder follow to achieve effective FLW prevention and reduction in their context? Mapping this journey into a clear process flow helps project partners align tools with stakeholder needs and guides both parties toward practical, action-oriented discussions. It also turns diverse project outputs into an integrated support pathway, showing stakeholders where they are in the process and what support is available at each step. In PRECIOUS, this approach is operationalised through a six-step process, which is grounded in the experiences of running behaviour change interventions and FLWPR-specific interventions under the Academy of Change and Chorizo projects, respectively (Strube & Nicolau, 2019; ICLEI European Secretariat, 2025).

Six Steps Used in PRECIOUS

The PRECIOUS project aims to reduce food loss and waste across all stages of the food supply chain. As a result, the process flow diagram was kept simple, focusing on the essential steps of designing and implementing FLWPR interventions. The diagram illustrates how various tools and outputs developed under PRECIOUS will provide value for stakeholders along each step. In addition to providing clear guidance on the type of support, which stakeholders can expect across supply chains, it also helps to integrate the various project activities in a practice-oriented manner.

Key Takeaways for Practitioners

- Map project outputs onto a user-centric process flow, providing a clear overview of tools and insights that a project can deliver towards the overarching objective.
- Process flows highlight how a complex project provides added value to (often voluntarily) participating stakeholders.
- The process flow can help to better integrate the various project activities.
- The mapping of the process provides an entry point to integrate the project's need for stakeholder feedback with stakeholders' interest in FLWPR.

Using a process-based approach allows research and innovation projects to frame project outputs in a way that is practical, intuitive, and aligned with stakeholder needs. It not only supports more meaningful engagement but also fosters stronger integration across diverse project activities—ultimately increasing the impact of food loss and waste prevention efforts.

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Keywords

Food loss and waste prevention, Stakeholder engagement, Process flow, Communities of Practice, Co-creation, Food supply chain sustainability, User-centric tools, Research-to-practice integration

About

Coordinated by the University of Deusto and comprising of 18 partners from 11 different European countries, the EU-funded PRECIOUS project seeks to build a systemic, multi-actor approach to Food Loss and Waste (FLW) prevention. The project will develop and share a standardised database of effective FLW prevention and reduction actions, addressing both their benefits and potential rebound effects. It also aims to create holistic methodologies that engage diverse food system stakeholders, incorporating sustainability science, climate change considerations, biodiversity preservation, and policy priorities into an integrated framework.

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Annex 3 – Practice abstracts in EIP-AGRI common format

Please see the following pages.

Raising Awareness and Reducing Food Loss and Waste Among Young Generations

Practice Abstract #1

Author: Leticia Lopez, EIT Food, leticia.lopez@eitfood.eu

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Problem, objectives and solutions

Food loss and waste (FLW) remain a global challenge, yet younger generations often lack engaging, age-appropriate educational resources to understand FLW and adopt preventive behaviours. Educational activities are often fragmented and poorly integrated into everyday life. The project addresses these gaps by supporting the development of sustainable habits at school, at home, and in communities.

Summary of findings and practical recommendations

- Ensure age-specific design of materials to balance scientific rigour with accessibility, particularly for primary and secondary school audiences.
- Prioritise experiential learning by integrating practical exercises, such as meal-planning challenges or food-repurposing tasks, to strengthen the real-world application of concepts.
- Strengthen continuity across education levels, ensuring alignment between school-focused materials, university curricula, and community activities to maximise long-term impact.
- Facilitate collaboration among schools, universities, and local organisations, creating multi-actor networks that reinforce behavioural change and extend the reach of FLW-prevention initiatives.
- Engage proactively with educational centres, prioritising schools already connected to our ecosystem to ensure smooth implementation and maximised impact.
- Equip teaching staff with high-quality, ready-to-use educational resources, providing clear value and tangible benefits for schools participating in the programme.

Target audience, practitioners, end users:

Educators, educational institutions, teachers, and stakeholder-engagement professionals.

Further information:

- Los Salvacomidas platform: <https://salvacomidas.eitfood.eu/>
- EIT Food Educators Programme: <https://www.eitfood.eu/projects/food-educators>

For more information regarding the results of the PRECIOUS project, please visit:

<https://www.precious-horizon.eu/resources/>

Keywords

Food Loss and Waste, education, youth engagement, sustainability, behavioural change, circular food systems, PRECIOUS.

Project name: Addressing the Environmental Impacts Of Food Loss And Waste Prevention And Its Rebound Effects

About

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Partners

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Consumer Acceptance of Upcycled Foods – Recommendations for Practitioners

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Practice Abstract #2

Problem, objectives and solutions

Upcycled foods can reduce food loss and waste by using safe, edible by-products and surplus ingredients, but they remain unfamiliar to most consumers. Low awareness, safety concerns and negative associations with “waste” limit acceptance. The project addresses the need for practical guidance on how to design, position and communicate upcycled foods that consumers trust and buy.

Summary of findings and practical recommendations

Based on this literature, some concrete suggestions for producers, retailers and communicators are:

- Focus on plant-based, upcycled ingredients in familiar formats, such as bread, biscuits, snack bars, and drinks. Where possible, link upcycled ingredients to existing quality cues (e.g. local, organic, traditional recipes).
- Ensure upcycled products look, taste and feel like “normal” food (or better). Clearly state that ingredients are safe and hygienically processed; avoid the word “waste” altogether.
- Explain upcycling briefly in consumer-friendly terms: avoiding waste and protecting the environment. Emphasise frugality and resourcefulness alongside sustainability.
- Use recognisable logos and certifications to signal upcycled content and environmental benefits. Tell short, concrete origin stories and invite consumers to imagine themselves enjoying the product.
- Avoid large price premiums unless health and sustainability benefits are very clear. For mainstream segments, frame upcycled products as “smart, good-value choices” that are both tasty and responsible.

Target audience, practitioners, end users:

Food manufacturers and processors, product developers and R&D teams, marketing and communication managers, retail companies, food businesses and customers.

Further information:

For more information regarding the results of the PRECIOUS project, please visit:

<https://www.precious-horizon.eu/resources/>

Keywords

Upcycled foods, food waste reduction, consumer acceptance, sustainable food systems, circular economy in food, food loss and waste prevention, sustainability communication, consumer behaviour in food choices

Project name: Addressing the Environmental Impacts Of Food Loss And Waste Prevention And Its Rebound Effects

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Using Process Flows to Increase Value for Stakeholder Participation in Food Loss and Waste Prevention

Practice Abstract #3

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Problem, objectives and solutions

Food loss and waste prevention and reduction (FLWPR) projects often generate multiple tools and outputs, while stakeholders have limited time and participate on a voluntary basis. This creates challenges in feedback and perceived added value. The project addresses this by improving how project outputs are structured and communicated to better support stakeholder participation.

Summary of findings and practical recommendations

By visualising the stakeholder journey in a clear process flow, diverse project outputs are integrated into a coherent support pathway. In PRECIOUS, this is operationalised through a simple six-step process covering essential stages of FLWPR intervention design and implementation.

Key Takeaways for Practitioners

- Map project outputs onto a user-centric process flow, providing a clear overview of tools and insights that a project can deliver towards the overarching objective.
- Process flows highlight how a complex project provides added value to participating stakeholders. It can help to better integrate the various project activities.
- The mapping of the process provides an entry point to integrate the project's need for stakeholder feedback with stakeholders' interest in FLWPR.

Using a process-based approach allows research and innovation projects to frame project outputs in a way that is practical, intuitive, and aligned with stakeholder needs. It not only supports more meaningful engagement but also fosters stronger integration across diverse project activities, ultimately increasing the impact of FLWPR efforts.

Target audience, practitioners, end users:

Researchers and innovation practitioners, facilitators of Communities of Practice (CoPs), stakeholder engagement professionals, NGOs and intermediaries, food supply chain stakeholders, policy makers engaging in FLW prevention initiatives, civil society organisations and project consortia.

Further information:

For more information regarding the results of the PRECIOUS project, please visit:

<https://www.precious-horizon.eu/resources/>

Keywords

Food loss and waste prevention, Stakeholder engagement, Process flow, Communities of Practice, Co-creation, Food supply chain sustainability, User-centric tools, Research-to-practice integration

Audiovisual material:

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